

SOME THOUGHTS ON POST-INDUSTRIAL SOCIETY AND THE NEW ROLES OF EMOTIONAL DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores new perspectives and concepts for Emotional Design understood as an approach that extends beyond material matters to the emotional responses, experiences, effects and social transformations that Design actions may produce. It brings some thoughts on the dematerialization of Design, collaborative consumption and Service Design and was motivated by the changing values, needs and interpretation of quality of life brought by the so called coming of post-industrial society.

Keywords: post-industrial society; dematerialization; services; collaboration; experience.

INTRODUCTION

The activity of design was conceived at the birth of an industrial society, formed and developed based on mass manufacturing and the production of tangible goods.

But today, the results from this practice are changing to a post-industrial paradigm (Bell, 1974). While the industrial society was based on materiality and goods manufacturing, the post-industrial society - as outlined by Daniel Bell in his book “The Coming of Post-Industrial Society” - will be information-led and service-oriented.

The author emphasizes an increase of the service sector as one important characteristic of the post-

industrial society and “a shift from an economy primarily based on goods production to one based on services” (Bell, 1974:126). He adds that the post-industrial society is also marked by the “information sector”, the centrality of human relationships and ‘intellectual technology’, based on information and computing technology.

Among the key values of the new emerging society we can also add a growing acceptance of and seek for spirituality; a collective consciousness based on global and local networks of information technology; a tolerance and even celebration of cultural, ethnic and sexual diversity; ecological and social awareness and the idea that using and sharing is better than owning.

In such a dematerialized economy and caring society the questions are: Is it possible to think of a non industrial or a non object oriented design? Is there a new mental model adjusted to the post-industrial reality? This paper attempts to answer these questions and was organized in five sections. The first presents some thoughts about the called “dematerialization of Design”; the second brings design concepts developed around the term collaboration; the third describes the state of the art of Service Design; the fourth refers to the Experience Based Method and the last one summarizes some possible perspectives for Emotional Design.

ON THE DEMATERIALIZATION OF DESIGN

In his suggestive article called "The Dematerialization of Design", Jorge Frascara (2002) recognizes we are going through a moment of change and the need to redefine the objectives of design and its working methods. Exploring a contemporary notion of design, he suggests a shift of focus from objects, materials and production processes to the effects they will have on society and the planet, the context in which they will be used, as well as their consequences on people's daily life. According to Frascara (2002) "Design is not concerned with objects, but with the impact that those objects have on people". The author also suggests a shift "from the design of objects to the design of situations and activities" or the "dematerialization of design".

In the same direction, Alexander Manu (1994) observes that "because designers create physical objects, they think of needs as having tangible shape. And product design tries to anticipate and meet the solid, mechanical needs of users."

Contributing to discussions, Ezio Manzini (2004) asserts that the project's object becomes "an event oriented to a result," indicating that "what is acquired is not a physical product, but an event that takes place in a certain place and at any given time and changes the status of the individual who acquired" hence "product-event should be seen as an artifact in four dimensions, where the fourth dimension is time". This change occurs through the interaction of several actors who cooperate to produce a certain value, and the events connected with this production value become the object of the project design.

The design's emancipation of the adjective "industrial" breaks new ground in the profession in the twenty-first century, enabling the activity to shape a variety of contemporary products (objects, and also not objects). Such as illustrated by Bertola (2004) "product design goes to the design of the 'supply' system of a company, and ever more frequently to the design of

life cycle of its offer, and also the dynamics of interaction between the user and product during use. It means that products design, today, includes services, experiences, environments, communications systems and other non-tangible forms.

Mike Press and Rachel Cooper (2003) also explore the context, practices and the new roles of designers in postindustrial times. For the authors, firstly, the essential characteristic of the designer is the fact that he was a maker. In other words, the activities and skills of making lies at the heart of the activity design. Secondly, design is a process of meaning making: each object, communication or designed environment provides human experiences and all of them carry meanings. By enabling meaning, the designer is a maker of culture, a cultural intermediary. Thirdly, the formation of the designer encourages creativity, originality and imagination, features highly valued in the post-industrial economy.

Recently, both companies and academia realized a potential for a new approach to design practice, which goes beyond the design of physical artifacts. John Thackara (2008) points out a new path for the design: from the possession to the consumption of goods (i.e. from the property for the use of products). The author states that, for this to occur, we need a cultural change.

In this context, it is vital to understand how design can contribute to the development of this type of project, innovating their practices and expanding its scope of action in the post-industrial times, including services and experiences design and considering "post materialist values", such as trust in oneself and the group, collaboration, self-esteem, self expression, among others.

ON COLLABORATIVE CONSUMPTION: NEW POSSIBILITIES TO DESIGN FOR SERVICES

Botsman and Rogers start to explain the Collaborative Consumption concept coined by them in their book *What's mine is yours: How Collaborative Consumption is changing the way we live* (2010) arguing us the following question: "Why is that we spend so much time teaching children how to share their toys nicely but for adults sharing becomes a loaded concept?" (p. 67). And then they continue: "We share our roads, parks, schools, and other public spaces, but we draw the line in other areas of our life, such as our personal belongings".

From this point on, they begin telling us about contemporary ways of consumption that result from a collaborative revolution that "has risen up and is gaining momentum throughout our culture, political and economical system" (p. 69). A revolution based in traditional cooperative attitudes like sharing, bartering, lending, trading, renting, gifting and swapping; all of them redefined by peer communities and through the use of new Information and Communication Technologies (ICT's).

To illustrate the proposal model, they show us project examples collected and divided by them in three different categories: Product Service Systems (PSS), redistribution markets and collaborative lifestyles. The project examples vary from bike and car sharing companies like the French *Velib* (<http://www.velib.paris.fr/>) or the American *Zipcar* (<http://www.zipcar.com/chicago/find-cars>), respectively; until swapping systems where used or pre owned goods are redistributed from where they are not needed to where they are, like in the giant American *Ebay* (<http://www.ebay.com/>) or the *ThredUp* (<http://www.thredup.com>). Not to mention still projects that support sharing and exchanging resources and assets like the social network called *Couch Surfing*, a hospitality service where people all over the world not only can socialize themselves with

everyone, but also can search for and get free places - in the house of friends until then unknown - to stay during their travels.

Permeated by principals like critical mass, idling capacity, belief in the commons and trust between strangers, the Collaborative Consumption model can profoundly impact the contemporary Design production, not only aligning with the post-industrial values already mentioned above, but also challenging modern notions such as individuality, autonomy, privacy, personal liberty, and so on.

The concepts behind the term Collaborative Consumption, though, are not so new for the scope of the Design studies. When we talk about PSS - an important western concept of servitization, firstly defined by Goedkoop *et al.* (1999) -, for instance, we can observe numerous approaches between the concept and the area. One of them, includes some of the training bases of the emerging discipline called Service Design.

The PSS concept is very important for the actual discussion about collaboration in the design field. It not only "extends the traditional functionality of a product by incorporating additional services" (Baines *et al.*, 2007), but also emphasizes, in this way, the "sale of use rather than the sale of product" (Baines *et al.*, 2007).

Still arguing about visions that had already been developed - in the design area - based in some of the concepts addressed by Botsman and Rogers (2010), we find also some one of the Thackara's work (2008). In the context of discussions on innovation and sustainability, the author addressed the importance of the activity in a "world with less stuffs and more people", by emphasizing both the design focus on services and systems (p. 17), and the power of the activity in conceptualizing "platforms that permit that

people interact in more effective and enjoyable ways” (p. 19).

To explore the fact that “alternative models of organization of daily life are being tried and tested worldwide” (p. 19), he quotes a large research made by Manzini - through the program of activities EMUDE (Emerging User Demands for Sustainable Solutions) - with an aim "to explore the potential of social innovations as a driven for technological and production innovation" (Jégou and Manzini, 2008).

The program of activities EMUDE resulted in two books, both of them made based on researches developed around the theme social innovation. The first book, edited by Anna Meroni and called *Creative Communities: People inventing sustainable ways of living* (2007), describes groups of “people who creatively solve social problems around them rather than complying with existing solutions that fail to meet their needs”. The second one, edited by Manzini and Jégou and called *Collaborative Services: Social innovation and design for sustainability* (2008), focused directly in the conceptualizing of a new scenario called Collaborative Services.

In this way, Collaborative Services are defined as services that are built by a group of people who co-create values and are recognized by mutual agreements. For this reason, organizations that offer this type of service are called collaborative organizations. What means that production and delivery of services are based on a collaborative relationship with peer-to-peer, and consequently, on a high level of confidence.

An example of this type of service is the Italian case of sharing homes called Lodge a Student at Home, where older people could stay in their homes with young students. The service aimed to understand the different lifestyles and needs of different stakeholders of the service (homeowners and guests) and

facilitates the sharing of the house among these people. Young students find cheap housing and family accommodation and the lonely elderly, an independent company (Jégou and Manzini, 2008).

ON SERVICE DESIGN

The origins of the study field called “service design” are in universities and consulting firms since the early'90s in three different countries: Germany - Michael Erlhoff and Birgit Mager, University of Applied Sciences in Cologne -; United Kingdom - Gillian and Bill Hollins -; and Italy - Ezio Manzini, Politecnico of Milano - (Saco, 2008).

For the knowledge bases which enabled the development of the service design field, we find areas related to product design, design for sustainability, interface design and interaction design. These areas transferred their established methods of analysis and transferred to the field of services.

The first approach adopted by researchers in the field, tended to define services as "products" (Hollins and Hollins, 1991) and because of that, they are tie to the design process. Hollins and Hollins (1991), from the perspective of total design, claims that services need to be designed and managed, orientating much of their work to the differences between the products and services from the perspective of the processes. The authors have a closest approach of engineering and management, relating the process of service design to the processes mapping and the specification of performance standards. Ramaswamy (1996), within the same perspective, understands that the essence of the service designer work is the design process, and this process must have a level of performance that exceeds the expectations of the User. It is up to the service designer to define the features, layout and aesthetics of facilities and delivery processes. As a result of his work, there would be product design (physical attributes of the service), facilities (layout of the touchpoint), operation process (activities required

to deliver a service) and customer service process (guides for interaction between supplier and user).

It was with the introduction of the paradigm of interaction that the design of services "began to build their identity and legitimize their work" (Sangiorgi, 2004). "This paradigm refers to the set of concepts, values and tools that derive from the interpretation of services and moments of interaction between the user and the provider".

The analogy between the interactions design (User-device interface) and services interaction (or services encounters) is at the heart and the origins of identity, language and practice of the field of design services. One feature that is being gradually modified in the last decade is the context and nature of interactions that the services design is faced: the interactions between suppliers and users from one-on-one interactions to many-to-many; from sequential interactions to open interactions; from within organizations to between organizations (Sangiorgi, 2004).

Since services are potential performances, i.e. only take place from the User Action, to design the aesthetics and the form of relationships, means to place the potentiality of these performances at the service interface, i.e. to create a set of instructions and representations that enable the User to interact. As the service interface is very complex (involving not only the environment and technical elements, but also the human apparatus) is necessary to understand the various types of interfaces (human or machine) to suit the nature of "software" that contains the act of potential enjoyment of services. Pacenti (2004) defines the service interface as the tangible part of a service that the User may experience, and is made up of people, products, information, and environment, which support the User Experience. Using the theatre's metaphor, the author characterizes the service design activities like creating a scene and choreography, expanding the scope of the project

beyond the form and aesthetic quality of the object or the environment, including the form and the aesthetic of interactions.

The service designer come to design tangible evidence that support a desirable experiences in a coherent way, as a film director who manages and integrates all elements of the scene to provide a particular experience. So, for a good service design interaction, designers must know the requirements for the interaction (common vocabulary) and the interaction models (metaphors, atmosphere and aesthetic qualities that give visibility to the service, and the degree of transparency of the provision) to strength the project's decisions (Paceti, 2004).

Since a change in the logic of building value in the service economy occurred, the researchers Rafael Ramirez and Ulf Mannervik (2008) have changed the linear model of understanding the "moments of truth" (places of interaction between customer-supplier), where producers and consumer co-produced and where the customers then evaluated the supplier. The authors present a new model for understanding the moment of truth: dynamic networks of building value. In this model, they state that increasingly, actors, resources and relationships are involved in activities of value creation, not involving the design of more moments of truth, but the co-evolution of the dynamics of systems of value creation. The competence of the designer is no longer the design of interfaces between objects, people and processes provided by an organization for a user. The designer come to design the key interactions that allow the value promised is co-produced by the customer and supplier. In a world of greater complexity and connectivity, the main challenge for the design is now navigation (or sense making) and enclave so that consumers are not only co-creating value, but also participating actively and positively in co-design and co-construction of the constellation of value.

According to Ramirez and Mannervik (2008) the service economy is a place where collaborative advantage is perhaps more important to the success than competitive advantage, and the design here, not only means designing objects, interfaces and contexts, but also design the dynamic system of relations. In this way, the studies of service design left to the operation of contextual and systemic dimensions of services in different ways and adopting different theories, with the aim of providing conceptual models and theoretical frameworks to assist designers in the observation, sense-making, and visualization of complex social systems (such as service organizations are).

In the PhD thesis, Daniela Sangiorgi presents one of these paths (2004) exploring the application of the Activity theory to the analysis and the design of services. Similar to the paradigm of interaction, activity theory in service design provided a framework to overcome the model one-to-one (User-Interface) and sequential (services scripts) of services interactions to include a wider system of actions and interactions. In this system, the service encounter is described as mediated by instruments located (evidence of the service), social aspects (people, rules and roles) and conditions (service interface), but is also located within the broader system of activities that each participant of the service belongs. The success of service design activity could be increased by synchronizing the perspectives, the objectives and the practices of service's participants (Sangiorgi, 2009). Clearly, the type of services in this paradigm are those considered experiential, i.e. those services where the focus is on the User Experience when it interacts with the organization, rather than focusing only on the benefits from the products and services delivered (Voss and Zomerdijs, 2007). The authors found that these services are often designed from the perspective of the consumer journey, rather than a single product or transaction. The service is seen as a

journey that lasts a longer period of time and consists of multiple components and multiple points of contact.

The shift in thinking and practice of design since the appearance of service design may reflect a shift in the thinking of design as a tool to boost consumption to become a tool for building new relationships between people and society (Young, 2008). This shift in the design theory focus from tangible products and artifacts to one focused on systems and services is a consequence of the evolution of the service sector proposed by Ramirez and Mannervik (2008) and of the technology itself. So, it must be understood how researchers comprehend the design changing, and how they are evolving the discipline construction.

A new way to understand the relationship between the user and the design activity began to emerge. At the same time, new design approaches were developed to deal with this reality. The projects are no longer focused on the user but now are developed with the user. Service design studios and researchers now recognize participatory design or co-design as a way of creating shared value in services. Oliver King (2009) - co-founder and director of Engine Service Design, United Kingdom - and Lavrans Løvlie (2009) - co-founder of live | work - United Kingdom - emphasize that the co-design is one of the most important practices of service design, as engages in the design process both the people who provide the service as the people who receive it.

With this type of work, the service design field of studies deepened the discussions on social and cultural impact of their actions on people's lives, bringing their work from public institutions and user communities. One important path of these discussions is about design methods for services. Hereafter, we will describe one important approach for designing services.

ON THE EXPERIENCE BASED METHOD

The experience-based design approach broadens the scope of human-centered design, considering not only the beliefs and behaviors, but also the sensations caused by user interaction with the services (Bate and Robert, 2007). In proposing the experience-based design (EBD) method, John Cain (1998) suggests to reorganize the design process around the knowledge about companies, their products and services, and around the experiences of people who interact with them. For the author, this would be the way to obtain more effective results of design solutions, namely: (1) when meeting the business goals of the organization, (2) when they become essential, or even central to people's lives, (3) when they are well designed or produced.

Cain (1998, p. 11) defines the EBD method as "a process that employs a deep understanding of the use and daily experience of people with the products and services, applying it to inform and shape the goals of business". In essence, it is a method to examine, interpret and organize the daily experience of people in a way that is useful for all actors involved in the design process. The author argues that this method improves the results of design, once integrates the design process around one guiding principle: how people act in real use situations or experiences. The users experiences are the core of the project. They must shape and guide the strategy, development and implementation of new products and services.

Cain (1998) lists the components of the experience as: (1) the sociocultural systems that inform ideas, beliefs, attitudes and expectations of users (think); (2) the patterns and routines of action, meaning and identity (do); (3) things that people use and their impact on what individuals think and do (use).

Through these three components, it is possible to describe the relationships between objects, people and environments and build frameworks of how

people relate to each other and how they experience some aspects of their world. For the author, the construction of these frameworks is essential for innovation, because they are the synthesis that serves as a bridge between the existing and the desirable.

For this, Cain (1998) proposes to use ethnographic research techniques to observe, describe and summarize those relationships. But unlike anthropologists, seeking only to understand the experiences, designers seek to know them to "be able to change it, improve it" (Cain, 1998, p.13). Designers always try to identify opportunities to transform existing realities in more desirable ones for the social agents who live in societies.

The EBD method consists of four goals, which serve to guide the team from the problem to final solution: (1) define and structure the problem in terms of user experience; (2) identify opportunities to change the current experiences; (3) invent solutions; (4) create the personification of solution, namely, tangible ways that give life and expression to the solutions.

SOME THOUGHTS ON THE NEW ROLES OF EMOTIONAL DESIGN IN POST INDUSTRIAL TIMES

Emotional Design is an approach that extends beyond material matters to the emotional responses, experiences, effects and social transformations that Design actions may produce and has important roles in post industrial times. It can promote new ways of consuming and help to change the meaning of consumption from buying things to using things. Designers, as cultural intermediaries, could use their creativity and imagination to reframe the meaning of consumption. For this purpose, the design discipline must shift its focus from designing products to designing services. Hence, it has to understand the user experience with products they own and translate them in new services that carry the meaning the users are really buying.

We suggest that experience based design could be an approach to design services that promote collaborative consumption mainly, in product-service systems and redistribution markets categories, because it incorporates both cognition and emotion in design process.

We claim that emotional design field could explore more its contribution to this kind of services. We believe that the use of ethnographic research techniques to observe, describe and summarize the owning experience of people with current products could contribute to design meaningful use experiences to foster collaborative consumption.

Emotional design could help to design collaborative services that are not only useful and usable, but also brings joy and pleasure in its use (like Zipcar). It also could help to build trust between strangers in order to encourage swapping services (like ThredUP). While, Zipcar example show us that it is possible to use a car instead of owning a car and still be considered cool by a new generation of consumers, thredUP built a platform that support trust between users, enabling moms buy, sell and swap children's clothes as they grow.

Concluding our thoughts on Post-Industrial Society and the new roles of Emotional Design, we think/believe that designers need to shift the focus from the interaction between people and objects to the interaction between people and people and understand products and services as mediators of social actions and relationships.

And, as the meaning and purpose of design is not in the product, but in the promotion of more desirable realities, we strongly believe that these are possible perspectives to the design practice. Mainly in such a dematerialized economy and caring society, where a viable way to think of a non object oriented design,

promises new mental model adjusted to the post-industrial reality.

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